

Extended Data 1.

Funnelled debriefing questionnaire

1. What do you think the purpose of the experiment was?
2. What were you trying to do during the task? Did you have any particular strategy or goal?
3. Did anything about the experiment seem strange or unusual?
4. Were you focusing on the number of dots the avatar could “see“ from its point of view?
(if „yes“) Why did you do that? Did something lead you to do that?

Extended Data 2.

Trial Types

Matched Trials Variants			
Word Prompt Colour	Number Prompt	Dots	Dot Colour
red	1	1	red
red	2	2	red
blue	1	1	blue
blue	2	2	blue

Mismatched Trials Variants			
Word Prompt Colour	Number Prompt	Dots	Dot Colour
red	0	1	red
red	0	2	red
red	1	2	red
red	1	1	blue
red	1	2	blue
red	2	1	red
red	2	1	blue
red	2	2	blue
blue	0	1	blue
blue	0	2	blue
blue	1	2	blue
blue	1	1	red
blue	1	2	red
blue	2	1	blue
blue	2	1	red
blue	2	2	red

Each of the test trial variants above represent 8 trial types based on combination of 3 further features i) the direction the avatar was facing (left vs right), ii) whether the avatar faced the location of the dots such that they saw the same number of dots as the participant (consistent vs inconsistent) and iii) the two stimulus onset asynchronies (0 ms and 300 ms).

For each block all matched trial variants were sampled twice (4 variants x 8 types x 2 samples) to create 32 matching trials and half of mismatched trials variants (16 variants x 8 types x 0.5 samples) were sampled to create 32 mismatching trials (the remaining half of the mismatched trial variants were used in a subsequent block to ensure each variant was presented the same number of times across the whole experiment).

